

SHORT NOTES

Pyridine Compounds of Pentavalent Rhenium

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The first example of pentavalent cationic rhenium complex, dioxo-bis-ethylenediamine-rhenium (V) chloride, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$, was reported by Lebedinskii and Inanov-Emin¹. Kotelnikova and Tronev², Lebedinskii and Inanov-Emin³, and Sur and Sen⁴ have reported the preparation of dioxo-tetrapyridine-rhenium (V) chloride, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$. A simpler method for the preparation of the compound with KReO_4 as the starting material is now described.

Procedure.—An intimate mixture of KReO_4 (1*M*) and KI (2.5*M*) was boiled with HCl (conc.) and freed from iodine by repeated evaporation with HCl (conc.) on a water bath. The dried mass was refluxed for 3 hours with excess of aqueous pyridine and filtered hot. The filtrate was crystallised in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . The crystals after separation were extracted with absolute ethanol and evaporated in vacuum. The large deep red crystals on analysis conform to the formula $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$. {Found: Re, 32.8; C, 41.5; H, 3.60; N, 9.67; Cl, 6.37. Calc. for $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$: Re, 32.7; C, 42.1; H, 3.51; N, 9.83; Cl, 6.23%}.

The compound is soluble in water and ethanol. It produces an intense pink coloration with HCl (conc.) which disappears on boiling with separation of a green substance. This product on analysis corresponds to the formula $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$. (Found: Re, 39.8; C, 25.9; H, 2.15; N, 5.86; Cl, 23.2. Calc. for $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$: Re, 39.8; C, 25.7; H, 2.14; N, 6.00; Cl, 22.8%).

The green substance is insoluble in all ordinary solvents except pyridine which forms a yellow solution. Pentavalency of rhenium in this compound is proved by $\text{Na}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ oxidation. Pentavalent oxytrichloride of rhenium is unknown, but here it has been stabilised by co-ordination with pyridine, a hexa-co-ordinated non-electrolyte being formed. Recently Loeck and Wilkinson⁵ have reported analogous compounds containing triphenylphosphine and triphenylarsine.

1. *J. Gen. Chem., U.S.S.R.*, 1943, 13, 253.

2. *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1958, 3, 1008

3. *Ibid.*, 1959, 4, 1762.

4. *Science & Culture*, 1960, 26, 85.

5. *Chem. Ind.*, 1962, 40.

Warming a solution of dioxo-tetrapyridine-rhenium chloride with excess KCN and subsequent crystallisation gave rise to well-known tripotassium dioxo-tetracyanorhenate (V), $K_3 [ReO_2(CN)_4]$. Thus the cationic pentavalent rhenium is converted to stable pentavalent anionic rhenium. Double decomposition of these cationic and anionic salts gave rise to the sparingly soluble, crystalline, golden yellow compound of the formula $[ReO_2py_4]_3[ReO_2(CN)_4]$. [Found: N, 11.6; Re 39.4%. Calc. N, 11.6; Re, 38.7%].

Three co-ordination isomers of the above compound having the simplest formula $ReO_2py_3(CN)$ have been prepared and are being studied, details of which will be published elsewhere.

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